

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Geophysical survey – Cime Bianche Lake

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE DN.2_RM3 - SUMMER

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	30/06/2024	Final document	Godio A. ¹

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This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Description

Site: the Cime Bianche basin is an artificial lake built for programmed snowmaking on the ski slopes, near the Cime Bianche pass (Val d'Ayas) at an altitude of about 3000 m a.s.l., with an area of about 15,000 m² and a maximum volume of water that can be invaded of about 50,000 m³. The dam is in earth material, with internal construction not known, with two main slopes along the West and South sides of the lake.

Data acquisition (July 2023): Andrea Vergano, Alberto Godio, Diego Franco, Stefano Vigna

Data processing: Chiara Colombero, Valeria Strallo

Technical report drafting: Alberto Godio

Objective: characterization with electrical and seismic tomography methods (refraction and MASW surface wave analysis) to verify the characteristics of the dam and to define digital technologies for the monitoring of hydraulic works in high altitude.

Equipment

- Syscal PRO 72 channels (Electrical resistivity tomography – ERT)
- Seismograph Geode - 72 channels (refraction tomography, surface waves)

B) Method

Several methods have been tested to check the reliability and the limits of the geophysical survey to detect the inner properties of the embankments of earthen dams, with attention to the logistical issue of operating at high elevation in severe conditions.

We adopted electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), seismic refraction tomography (SRT) and surface waves survey (MASW). Rayleigh waves are a type of surface wave that propagates along the surface of the Earth. They are sensitive to the shear velocity of the subsurface. P-waves, or compressional waves, are a type of seismic wave that travels through both solids and liquids; they are the fastest type of seismic wave and are often used to image the subsurface. Shear waves, or S-waves, are another type of seismic wave that travels only through solids. They are slower than P-waves and are sensitive to the shear modulus of the material through which they travel. Surface waves are a type of seismic wave that propagates along the surface of the Earth. The dispersion of surface waves is sensitive to the shear-wave velocity of the subsurface. The integration of P-wave and S-wave results allow to estimate the mechanical properties of the materials; particularly, the Poisson's ratio is a dimensionless number that relates the ratio of lateral strain to vertical strain in a material, the Young's modulus is a measure of the stiffness of a material. It is defined as the ratio of stress to strain, the shear modulus is a measure of a material's resistance to shearing deformation.

The seismic refraction surveys were conducted using a sledgehammer as the energy source and geophones to record the seismic waves. The geophones were spaced at either 3 meters or 2 meters apart, depending on the survey. The seismic waves were generated by striking a steel plate with the sledgehammer, and the geophones recorded the time it took for the waves to travel through the subsurface. This data was then used to create a cross-sectional image of the subsurface, showing the different layers of rock and soil and their respective seismic velocities. The resistivity tomography is a geophysical method that uses electrical resistivity measurements to image the subsurface. The depth of investigation is typically limited by the electrical conductivity of the subsurface. Resistivity is a measure of a material's ability to resist the flow of electric current. Lower resistivity values indicate that a material is more conductive, while higher resistivity values indicate that a material is more resistive. More conductive materials on the uppermost part of the section usually limit the penetration depth. The presence of water in the subsurface can lower the electrical resistivity of the materials. The electrical resistivity surveys were conducted using Wenner-Schlumberger and Dipole-Dipole configuration array of electrodes to measure the electrical resistivity of the subsurface. The WS configuration is generally more sensitive to vertical variations in electrical resistivity, the DP-DP configuration is more sensitive to horizontal variations in the observed parameter. The choice of electrode configuration can affect the resolution and depth of penetration of the ERT survey. The WS configuration is generally better for imaging deep structures, while the DP-DP configuration is better for imaging shallow structures. The electrodes were spaced at 3 meters for profile 1 and 2 meters apart for profile 2. The electrical resistance of the subsurface was measured by injecting a current into the ground and measuring the voltage drop between the electrodes. This data was then used to create a cross-sectional image of the subsurface, showing the different layers of rock and soil and their respective electrical resistivities.

Seismic Refraction Tomography (two profiles)

Seismic Survey 1: 72 geophones spaced at 3 meters

Energy source: Impact of a sledgehammer on a steel plate at every 4 geophones

Seismic Survey 2: 72 geophones spaced at 2 meters

Energy source: Impact of a sledgehammer on a steel plate at every 4 geophones

Electrical Resistivity Tomography (two profiles)

Electrical Resistivity Survey 1: 72-meter array with electrodes spaced at 3 meters

Electrical Resistivity Survey 2: 72-meter array with electrodes spaced at 2 meters

The ERT profile 1 was conducted on the dam crest along the West side of the lake, with the first electrode (Start point) toward North and the End point at South. The Seismic Refraction Tomography (SRT) Survey 1 Overlaps with ERT profile 1

ERT profile 2 were performed with 72 electrodes with 2-meter spacing; the profile was partially located on the dam crest (south side) and partially descending towards the west along the dam

face and then on the in-place morainic material. The starting point (0 m – electrode 1) was located to the West side. The SRT profile 2 overlaps with ERT profile 2.

The Electrical Resistivity Measurements were performed using two different electrode configurations: Wenner-Schlumberger (WS) with 1287 quadrupoles; Dipole-Dipole (DP-DP) with 1286 quadrupoles. Each quadrupole consists of four electrodes: a current source (C1), a current sink (C2), a potential measuring electrode (P1), and a potential reference electrode (P2).

The Site

Figure 1 - the Cime Bianche lake with location of the tow profiles of ERT and SRT; the starting point of profile 1 (yellow) is located at North; the origin of the profile 2 (red) was at West.

Data Processing

The ERT data was processed using the open-source ResIPy (Rücker et al, 2017) software. The raw data was pre-processed by correcting the electrode spacing and filtering out apparent resistivity measurements with a standard deviation greater than 3% of the mean value.

The SRT data for P-waves was processed using custom-developed Matlab codes for the pre-processing phase (picking of first arrival times between the source and receiver, creation of the survey geometry) and an open-source Python code from the PyGIMLi library (Blanchy et al., 2020). This latter code allows for the tomographic processing of seismic data (travel times) to obtain a vertical section of P-wave velocity.

The surface wave data was processed using custom-developed Matlab codes to perform the following main operations: windowing of the seismograms of each explosion with a moving window of 12 receivers and a shift along the line of 1 receiver; calculation of the frequency-phase velocity spectrum for each window; stacking of the spectra related to the same window but obtained with a different source position

The dispersion curves of Rayleigh waves (fundamental mode) were obtained by picking the maxima of the stacked spectra. The dispersion curves were inverted using a laterally constrained inversion algorithm, which allows for the introduction of constraints on the variations of S-wave velocity and layer thickness along the investigated section.

The result of the Rayleigh wave processing reproduces a vertical section of S-wave velocity distribution.

The integration of P-wave and S-wave data allows for the derivation of a vertical section of the distribution of some mechanical parameters of potential interest, including Poisson's ratio, Young's modulus, and shear modulus.

Notes:

- ResIPy is an open-source software for ERT data processing; it provides a variety of tools for data preprocessing, inversion, and visualization.
- PyGIMLi is an open-source Python library for geophysical inversion; it includes a variety of tools for processing SRT data, as first arrival picking and travel time tomography.

C) Results

The results of the resistivity tomography processing for profile 1 are shown in Figure 2; a maximum investigation depth of about 40 meters below the ground level is achieved with the dipole-dipole configuration.

Figure 2 - Profile 1 - top) Electrical resistivity section acquired with the Wenner-Schlumberger electrode configuration; bottom) Electrical resistivity section acquired with the dipole-dipole electrode configuration.

The electrical resistivity sections shown in Figure 2 represent the distribution of electrical resistivity in the subsurface along profile 1 for the two different configuration arrays (WS and DP-

DP). The resistivity values are represented by colors, with higher resistivity values corresponding to blue colors and lower resistivity values corresponding to red colors.

The observed resistivity values range between 500 ohm-m and 60,000 ohm-m. The lower values refer to the material constituting the earthen dam, while the higher values are attributable to the bedrock or the presence of cavities, such as the drainage channel evident in the dipole-dipole configuration results at the coordinate of 120 m.

A low-resistivity anomaly is identified at coordinates 75-100 m, visible in both results but particularly evident in the dipole-dipole section. This anomaly is likely associated with a zone of higher moisture content in the material constituting the dam.

Figure 3 - Profile 2 - top) Electrical resistivity section acquired with the Wenner-Schlumberger electrode configuration; bottom) Electrical resistivity section acquired with the dipole-dipole electrode configuration.

In the resistivity section for profile 2 (Figure 3), there is no particular evidence of anomalies associated with the presence of regions of high saturation; the low-resistivity superficial detrital cover material is distinguished from the bedrock with high electrical resistivity values.

Figure 4 - Profile 1 - top) P-wave velocity distribution section; bottom) Shear-wave velocity distribution, from surface wave processing.

Figure 4 shows the P-wave and S-wave velocity sections for profile 1; the S-wave section is only partially reconstructed, from surface wave data, up to coordinate 160 m. For higher distances, the data quality was not sufficient for the correct extraction of surface wave dispersion curves, from which the S-wave velocity values can be obtained.

For the part of the section where the P-wave and S-wave velocity values overlap, it was possible to obtain the distribution sections of the Poisson's ratio, the bulk modulus and the shear modulus, shown in Figure 5. An average density value of 1900 kg/m³ was used to calculate the bulk and shear modulus values.

Figure 5 - profile 1 - top) vertical section of the Poisson module; centre) Shear module; bottom) Young's module.

Figure 6 - Synthesis of the results obtained along profile 1, comparison between the electrical resistivity section (top), compressional wave velocities (center) and shear wave velocities (bottom).

The figure 6 provides a comprehensive overview of the geophysical data collected along profile 1; the top panel shows the electrical resistivity section, which reflects the distribution of electrical conductivity in the subsurface; the middle panel shows the compressional wave velocity section, which indicates the velocity at which P-waves propagates through the subsurface. The bottom panel shows the shear wave velocity section, which indicates the speed at which S-waves travel through the subsurface. By comparing these three sections, it is possible to gain a more detailed understanding of the subsurface structure and properties along profile 1; particularly, it is confirmed the detection of the bedrock at the depth of 15 m and the detection of weaker region at coordinate 100-120 m, that also corresponds to an electrical anomaly.

Figure 7 - Profile 2 - top) P-wave velocity distribution; bottom) S-wave velocity distribution; Processing was not possible for values at coordinates above 80 m.

The figure 7 shows the distribution of P-wave and S-wave velocities along profile 2; the P-wave velocity distribution (top panel) indicates the variation of P-wave velocity with depth along the profile. The higher P-wave velocity at the bottom refer to the more rigid material (bedrock). The S-wave velocity distribution (bottom panel) shows the variation of S-wave velocity with depth along the profile: the higher the S-wave velocity, the stiffer the material (bedrock).

For profile 2, the seismic and electrical alignment partially covered the external embankment in the South-East area of the section. The velocity models obtained along this profile are shown in Figure 7. An estimate of the mechanical parameters is given in Figure 8.

The results of the seismic and electrical surveys are compared in Figure 9. Both electrical tomography and seismic data identify the transition at a depth of about 10 m from the ground level between the superficial cover material (detrital) and the compact bedrock. The latter is characterized by P-wave velocity values of about 4500-5000 m/s and S-wave velocity values of about 1800-2000 m/s.

Along this profile, no anomalous variations in the water content of the embankment materials were detected.

Figure 8 - profile 2 - top) vertical section of the Poisson module; centre) Shear module; bottom) Young's module

Figure 9 - Synthesis of the results obtained along profile 2, comparison between the electrical resistivity section (top), compressional wave velocities (center) and shear wave velocities (bottom).

D) References

- Blanchy G., Saneiyani S., Boyd J., McLachlan P. and Binley A. 2020. "ResIPy, an Intuitive Open Source Software for Complex Geoelectrical Inversion/Modeling." Computers & Geosciences, February, 104423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2020.104423>.
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